

MATHEMATICAL BEASTS

The Strenuous Questions

A Research Work

By Badarauta Yougander (Yougi)

Independent researcher

Forged with Thoughts

MATHEMATICUS QUESTIONS

THE STRENUOUS QUESTIONS

R

$$\int_0^{\infty} x^2 y dA$$

$$\Gamma(z) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{-1} e^{-t} dt$$

Abstract

In this context we will be dealing with some of the strenuous questions which need attention and deep conceptual understanding. These are made by me, I remember the time when I was working on some trigonometric questions then after analyzing how the questions are made my creativity + concept understanding blended some of the strenuous questions. I gave some of the hardest questions to my friends to see if they can solve it, and I was glad very few made it to the answer and some questions are just so tough that sometimes even I forget how to solve them and these questions can be solved in different ways. So, this context only contains the strenuous questions which may define or represent my creativity and understanding.

Author's Introduction

I am Badarauta Yougender, born in the town of Jeypore, Odisha (India) My friends often call me Yougi and I'm 17 years old as of July 6, 2025. I am currently in 12th grade while writing this volume.

My interests include Mathematics, Theoretical physics, and I have a lot of curiosity about mathematics. Among these, I love mathematics so much that, I can spend a whole day working on them, as they never bore me.

After completing my 11th grade successfully, my mind started heading in a different directions. I realized that I can merge some concepts. Although I am not sure if that's commonly done. Then I began jotting down my ideas on a paper and now this Research paper is demonstration of that work. I never thought that I would be writing a Set of concepts one day but it happened. This is my place where you can find some of the strenuous questions that have the potential to make the reader thinking twice before solving it.

So, This is where you get to take a glance and indulge in some strenuous questions (with brief solutions) Which I guess have the potential to make the reader think at least twice before solving it.

Where the book ends, I begin

~Yougi

Question 1 (Logarithmic Simplification)

Find the value of

$$\frac{\ln(\prod_{i=1}^n 2^i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n i \ln(2)}$$

Difficulty: EASY

Prerequisites: Logarithms, Summations and product notations

Solution: To simplify this question we need to expand the notations

$$\prod_{i=1}^n 2^i = 2^1 \times 2^2 \times 2^3 \dots 2^n, \quad \sum_{i=1}^n i \ln(2) = \ln(2) + 2 \ln(2) + \dots + n \ln(2)$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\ln(\prod_{i=1}^n 2^i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n i \ln(2)} = \frac{\ln(2^1 \times 2^2 \times 2^3 \times \dots \times 2^n)}{\ln(2) + 2\ln(2) + 3\ln(2) + \dots + n \ln(2)}$$

Using the properties of logarithms $\Rightarrow a \ln(b) = \ln(b)^a$, $\ln(a) + \ln(b) = \ln(ab)$

$$\text{so,} \quad \Rightarrow \ln(2) + 2 \ln(2) + 3 \ln(2) + \dots + n \ln(2) = \ln(2 \times 2^2 \times 2^3 \dots 2^n)$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\ln(\prod_{i=1}^n 2^i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n i \ln(2)} = \frac{\ln(2 \times 2^2 \times 2^3 \times \dots \times 2^n)}{\ln(2 \times 2^2 \times 2^3 \times \dots \times 2^n)}$$

$$\Rightarrow \boxed{\frac{\ln(\prod_{i=1}^n 2^i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n i \ln(2)} = 1}$$

So, this question is relatively easy which requires the basic knowledge of logarithms, the use of summation and product notations. I guess this will be the easiest question among the all.

Question 2 (Bivariate Integration)

Evaluate the bivariate integral:

$$\int_{x=0}^{x=2} \int_{y=0}^{y=4} (xye^{x^2+y^2}) dy \cdot dx$$

Difficulty: MEDIUM

Prerequisites: Bivariate manipulation, Dealing with double integrals

Solution: To solve this question let us take $x^2 = t$ and $y^2 = u$ such that when differentiating these equations to get the equivalent values of dx and dy .

$$\Rightarrow \frac{d}{dx}(x^2) = \frac{d}{dx}(t) , \frac{d}{dy}(y^2) = \frac{d}{dy}(u)$$

$$\Rightarrow 2x = \frac{dt}{dx} , 2y = \frac{du}{dy}$$

$$\Rightarrow x \cdot dx = \frac{dt}{2} , y \cdot dy = \frac{du}{2}$$

We proceed by transforming the integration bounds accordingly.

if $x \rightarrow 0 \Rightarrow t \rightarrow 0$, if $x \rightarrow 2 \Rightarrow t \rightarrow 4$; if $y \rightarrow 0 \Rightarrow u \rightarrow 0$, if $y \rightarrow 4 \Rightarrow u \rightarrow 16$

So, the new integral becomes:

$$\int_{t=0}^{t=4} \int_{u=0}^{u=16} (e^{x^2+y^2}) (y \cdot dy) \cdot (x \cdot dx)$$

$$\int_{t=0}^{t=4} \int_{u=0}^{u=16} (e^{x^2+y^2}) \left(\frac{du}{2}\right) \left(\frac{dt}{2}\right)$$

$$\int_{t=0}^{t=4} \int_{u=0}^{u=16} \left(\frac{e^{(t+u)}}{4}\right) du \cdot dt$$

$$= \frac{1}{4} \int_{t=0}^{t=4} \int_{u=0}^{u=16} (e^t \cdot e^u) du \cdot dt$$

Now applying the rule: $\int \int f(x) \cdot g(y) dx \cdot dy = \{\int f(x) dx\} \{\int g(y) dy\}$ we get,

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{4} \left(\int_{t=0}^{t=4} e^t \cdot dt \right) \left(\int_{u=0}^{u=16} e^u \cdot du \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{4} ([e^t]_{t=0}^{t=4}) ([e^u]_{u=0}^{u=16}) \\ &= \frac{1}{4} (e^4 - e^0)(e^{16} - e^0) \\ &= \frac{1}{4} (e^4 - 1)(e^{16} - 1) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the integral evaluates to the simplified expression as given below.

$$= \boxed{\frac{1}{4} (e^{20} - e^{16} - e^4 + 1)}$$

So this question is moderately tough but the right substitution and the presence of mind lead you to the door of answer.

Question 3 (Trigonometric proof)

If $\sin\theta + \sin\Phi = t_1$; $\cos\theta + \cos\Phi = t_2$ and $t_1 \neq t_2$, Then prove that:

$$\cos(\theta + \Phi) = \frac{t_2^2 - t_1^2}{t_2^2 + t_1^2},$$

Difficulty: EASY

Prerequisites: Trigonometric Functions, Inverse Trigonometric Functions.

Solution: Given that $\sin\theta + \sin\Phi = t_1$, $\cos\theta + \cos\Phi = t_2$

Then applying the sum to product trigonometric identities we get,

$$\Rightarrow 2\sin\left(\frac{\theta+\Phi}{2}\right)\cos\left(\frac{\theta-\Phi}{2}\right) = t_1 \dots (i) , 2\cos\left(\frac{\theta+\Phi}{2}\right)\cos\left(\frac{\theta-\Phi}{2}\right) = t_2 \dots (ii)$$

Now dividing equation (i) by equation (ii) we get ,

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\left(2\sin\left(\frac{\theta+\Phi}{2}\right)\cos\left(\frac{\theta-\Phi}{2}\right)\right)}{\left(2\cos\left(\frac{\theta+\Phi}{2}\right)\cos\left(\frac{\theta-\Phi}{2}\right)\right)} = \frac{t_1}{t_2}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\sin\left(\frac{\theta+\Phi}{2}\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{\theta+\Phi}{2}\right)} = \frac{t_1}{t_2}$$

$$\Rightarrow \tan\left(\frac{\theta+\Phi}{2}\right) = \frac{t_1}{t_2}$$

Now using the $\tan\left(\frac{x}{2}\right)$ identity i.e., $\tan\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{1-\cos x}{1+\cos x}}$ we get

$$\Rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{1-\cos\left(2\left(\frac{\theta+\Phi}{2}\right)\right)}{1+\cos\left(2\left(\frac{\theta+\Phi}{2}\right)\right)}} = \frac{t_1}{t_2}$$

$$\Rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{1-\cos(\theta+\Phi)}{1+\cos(\theta+\Phi)}} = \frac{t_1}{t_2}$$

→ Squaring both sides we get,

$$\Rightarrow \left(\sqrt{\frac{1-\cos(\theta+\Phi)}{1+\cos(\theta+\Phi)}} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{t_1}{t_2} \right)^2$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1-\cos(\theta+\Phi)}{1+\cos(\theta+\Phi)} = \frac{t_1^2}{t_2^2}$$

$$\Rightarrow t_2^2[1 - \cos(\theta + \Phi)] = t_1^2[1 + \cos(\theta + \Phi)]$$

$$\Rightarrow t_2^2 - t_2^2 \cos(\theta + \Phi) = t_1^2 + t_1^2 \cos(\theta + \Phi)$$

$$\Rightarrow t_1^2 \cos(\theta + \Phi) + t_2^2 \cos(\theta + \Phi) = t_2^2 - t_1^2$$

$$\Rightarrow (t_1^2 + t_2^2) \cos(\theta + \Phi) = t_2^2 - t_1^2$$

$$\Rightarrow \boxed{\cos(\theta + \Phi) = \frac{t_2^2 - t_1^2}{t_2^2 + t_1^2}}$$

This question is completely based on the trigonometric functions. Anyone with a solid grasp of trigonometric identities will find this problem approachable, also there are different approaches to the solution of the question. Some basic algebra is also used in which we separated the “t” terms as given in the question above.

Question 4 (Riemann's Sum)

Find the value of **I** if:

$$I = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{n} \left\{ \frac{\left(\left(\frac{\ln a}{e^{\frac{k}{n}}} \right) + a^{-\frac{k}{n}} \right)}{\left(ae \right)^{-\frac{k}{n}} + \left(\frac{a}{e} \right)^{\frac{k}{n}} + \left(\frac{e}{a} \right)^{\frac{k}{n}} + 2} \right\} \left\{ \tan^{-1} \left(e^{\frac{k}{n}} + a^{\frac{k}{n}} \right) \right\}$$

Difficulty: VERY HARD

Prerequisites: Riemann's Sum , Evaluation of Limits, Exponential functions, Integration

Solution: The question contains a Riemann's Sum, we know that the Riemann's sum is given by

$$\int_0^1 f(x). dx = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{n} f\left(\frac{i}{n}\right)$$

So on comparison of Riemann's Sum and the question we see a similarity of $f\left(\frac{i}{n}\right)$ in Riemann sum and $f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)$ in the given question so, we can take $x = \frac{k}{n}$, as $dx = \frac{1}{n}$

The question reduces to:

$$\begin{aligned} &= \int_0^1 \left\{ \frac{\left(\left(\frac{\ln a}{e^x} \right) + a^{-x} \right)}{\left(ae \right)^{-x} + \left(\frac{a}{e} \right)^x + \left(\frac{e}{a} \right)^x + 2} \right\} \left\{ \tan^{-1} \left(e^x + a^x \right) \right\} dx \\ &= \int_0^1 \left\{ \frac{\left(\frac{\ln a}{e^x} + \frac{1}{a^x} \right)}{\left(\frac{1}{(ae)^x} \right) + \left(\frac{a}{e} \right)^x + \left(\frac{e}{a} \right)^x + 2} \right\} \left\{ \tan^{-1} \left(e^x + a^x \right) \right\} dx \\ &= \int_0^1 \left\{ \frac{\frac{a^x \ln a + e^x}{e^x a^x}}{1 + a^{2x} + e^{2x} + 2e^x a^x} \right\} \left\{ \tan^{-1} \left(e^x + a^x \right) \right\} dx \end{aligned}$$

$$= \int_0^1 \frac{a^x \ln a + e^x}{1 + (a^{2x} + e^{2x} + 2a^x e^x)} \{\text{Tan}^{-1}(e^x + a^x)\} dx$$

$$= \int_0^1 \frac{a^x \ln a + e^x}{1 + (a^x + e^x)^2} \{\text{Tan}^{-1}(e^x + a^x)\} dx \dots (i)$$

Now, let $\text{Tan}^{-1}(e^x + a^x) = z$, The boundaries of new integral will be

If $x \rightarrow 0 \Rightarrow z \rightarrow \text{Tan}^{-1}(2)$, if $x \rightarrow 1 \Rightarrow z \rightarrow \text{Tan}^{-1}(e + a)$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{d}{dx} \{\text{Tan}^{-1}(e^x + a^x)\} = \frac{d}{dx} (z)$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{e^x + a^x \ln a}{1 + (e^x + a^x)^2} = \frac{dz}{dx}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{e^x + a^x}{1 + (e^x + a^x)^2} dx = dz$$

Substituting the values with z and dz the new integral will be

$$= \int_{\text{Tan}^{-1}(2)}^{\text{Tan}^{-1}(e+a)} z dz$$

$$= \left[\frac{z^2}{2} \right]_{\text{Tan}^{-1}(2)}^{\text{Tan}^{-1}(e+a)}$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[(\text{Tan}^{-1}(e + a))^2 - (\text{Tan}^{-1}(2))^2 \right]$$

This question is somewhat difficult and requires the deep understanding of Riemann's sum. It took me about 10-15 minutes to make this question.

Question 5 (Functional Composition)

If $f(x) = k$ and also $nf(x) = [g(h(x))]^k, \forall x \in R$ where n is a integral Multiple and k is a non-zero constant. If $g(7) = 0$ then find the value of $h(x) \forall x \in R, \frac{d}{dx}[g(h(x))] \neq 0$

Difficulty: MEDIUM

Prerequisites: Functions handling, Algebra and differentiation.

Solution: Given that $f(x) = k$, where 'k' is a non-zero constant.

$$\Rightarrow nf(x) = nk \dots (i)$$

$$\text{Then we have } nf(x) = [g(h(x))]^k \dots (ii)$$

Now equating equation (i) and (ii) we get

$$\Rightarrow [g(h(x))]^k = nk$$

Differentiating both sides with respect to x we get,

$$\Rightarrow \frac{d}{dx} [g(h(x))]^k = \frac{d}{dx} (nk)$$

$$\Rightarrow k[g(h(x))]^{k-1} \cdot g'(h(x)) \cdot h'(x) = 0 \quad \left[\because \frac{d}{dx}(\text{constant}) = 0, \frac{d}{dx}f(g(x)) = f'(g(x)) \cdot h'(x) \right]$$

$$\Rightarrow k[g(h(x))]^{k-1} = 0 \quad \text{[Given that}$$

$$\Rightarrow g(h(x)) = 0 \text{ and given that } g(7) = 0 \Rightarrow g^{-1}(0) = 7$$

$$\Rightarrow h(x) = g^{-1}(0)$$

$$\Rightarrow \boxed{h(x) = 7}$$

This question involves the differentiation concept in order to find out the value of the inner function from the given composite function.

Question 6 (Real and imaginary)

Simplify the expression given below where $\text{Re}(e^{ie^x})$ is the real part and $\text{Im}(e^{ie^x})$ is the imaginary parts of Complex number e^{ie^x}

$$\text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\text{Re}(e^{ie^x})}{\sqrt{1 + \text{Im}(e^{ie^x})}} \right\} + \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \text{Im}(e^{ie^x})}} \right\}$$

Difficulty: HARD

Prerequisites: Trigonometric Identities and Inverse Trigonometric Identities, Euler's Formula.

Solution: We know that Euler's Formula is given by $e^{ix} = \text{Cos}x + i \text{Sin}x$

$$\Rightarrow e^{ie^x} = \text{Cos}(e^x) + i \text{Sin}(e^x)$$

Then the real part and the imaginary parts of this complex will be $\text{Cos}(e^x)$ and $\text{Sin}(e^x)$ Respectively,

$\Rightarrow 1\text{Re}(e^{ie^x}) = \text{Cos}(e^x)$, $\text{Im}(e^{ie^x}) = \text{Sin}(e^x)$, So then:

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\text{Re}(e^{ie^x})}{\sqrt{1 + \text{Im}(e^{ie^x})}} \right\} + \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \text{Im}(e^{ie^x})}} \right\} &= \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\text{Cos}(e^x)}{\sqrt{1 + \text{Sin}(e^x)}} \right\} + \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \text{Sin}(e^x)}} \right\} \\ &= \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\text{Cos}\left(2\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)\right)}{\sqrt{1 + \text{Sin}\left(2\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)\right)}} \right\} + \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \text{Sin}\left(2\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)\right)}} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Applying $\text{Sin}(2\theta)$ and $\text{Cos}(2\theta)$ and expanding 1 with $\text{Cos}^2\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) + \text{Sin}^2\left(\frac{x}{2}\right)$ we get,

$$= \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\text{Cos}^2\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) - \text{Sin}^2\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}{\sqrt{\text{Cos}^2\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) + \text{Sin}^2\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) + 2\text{Sin}\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)\text{Cos}\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}} \right\} + \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{Cos}^2\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) + \text{Sin}^2\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) - 2\text{Sin}\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)\text{Cos}\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}} \right\}$$

Perfect squaring and factorizing of both the terms inside Cot^{-1} we get,

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\left(\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) + \sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) \right) \left(\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) \right)}{\sqrt{\left(\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) + \sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) \right)^2}} \right\} + \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) \right)^2}} \right\} \\
&= \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) \right\} + \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

Now we know that $\text{Cot}^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) = \text{Tan}^{-1}(x)$ and $\text{Tan}^{-1}(x) + \text{Cot}^{-1}(x) = \pi/2$

$$= \text{Cot}^{-1} \left(\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) \right) + \text{Tan}^{-1} \left(\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) \right) = \boxed{\frac{\pi}{2}}$$

This can be solved in alternative method where,

$\text{Cot}^{-1}(x) + \text{Cot}^{-1}(y) = \text{Cot}^{-1}\left(\frac{xy-1}{x+y}\right)$ formula comes into action

$$\begin{aligned}
&\Rightarrow \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\cos(e^x)}{\sqrt{1+\sin(e^x)}} \right\} + \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\sin(e^x)}} \right\} = \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\left(\left(\frac{\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}{\sqrt{1+\sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}} \right) - 1 \right)}{\frac{\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}{\sqrt{1+\sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}}} \right\} \\
&= \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\left(\frac{\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)} - 1 \right)}{\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) - \sqrt{1+\sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

Here the numerator will be 0 as $\frac{\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)} - 1 = 1 - 1 = 0$ and $\frac{0}{\text{anything except } 0} = 0$

$$\Rightarrow \text{Cot}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\left(\frac{\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)} - 1 \right)}{\cos\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right) - \sqrt{1+\sin\left(\frac{e^x}{2}\right)}} \right\} = \text{Cot}^{-1}(0) = \boxed{\frac{\pi}{2}}$$

Question 7 (Melting Ice Cube)

A solid ice cube of edge length 'a' is melted by successively casting hot solid metal spheres into it, one after another. The radii of the spheres are $r_1, r_2, r_3, \dots, r_n$ where $r_1 > r_2 > r_3 \dots > r_n$, if this process continues indefinitely (i. e., $n \rightarrow \infty$), and all the ice is exactly melted with no loss of material, express the initial edge length of the cube in terms of the radii of the spheres.

Difficulty: HARD

Prerequisites: Volumes, Infinite Geometric Series, Limits, Algebra

Solution: The initial Volume of cube (V_0) = a^3

Now, each time a hot solid metal sphere is casted

In it the cube loses half of its volume every time i.e.

➤ Sphere with radius r_1 is casted into cube then

half of volume of cube is melted i.e., $\frac{a^3}{2}$

➤ Then sphere with radius r_2 is casted into the cube

then half of remaining volume is melted i.e., $\frac{\frac{a^3}{2}}{2} = \frac{a^3}{4}$

➤ Similarly after casting the sphere with radius r_n

the volume of cube melted will be $\frac{\frac{a^3}{2^{n-1}}}{2} = \frac{a^3}{2^n}$.

Then the volume of sphere with radius r_i = The volume of cube melted

$$\Rightarrow \frac{4}{3} \pi r_i^3 = \frac{a^3}{2^i}$$

$$\Rightarrow r_i^3 = \frac{3a^3}{4\pi 2^i} \dots (i)$$

Let the volume of spheres be $V_1, V_2, V_3, \dots, V_n$ with radii $r_1, r_2, r_3, \dots, r_n$.

Then, Volume of (i^{th}) Sphere = $\frac{4}{3}\pi r_i^3$ and substituting r_i with equation (i) we get

$$\text{Volume of sphere} = \frac{4}{3}\pi \left(\frac{3a^3}{4\pi 2^i}\right) = \frac{a^3}{2^i}$$

The question says that the process continues indefinitely $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{a^3}{2^i} &= \left(a^3 \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^i} \right) \\ &= a^3 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^3} + \dots + \frac{1}{2^{\infty}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Geometric sum is given by $a_1 \left(\frac{1-r^n}{1-r}\right)$, where a_1 is first term and r is common ratio

$$\Rightarrow a^3 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^3} + \dots + \frac{1}{2^{\infty}} \right) = a^3 \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1 - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{\infty}}{1 - \frac{1}{2}} \right) \right]$$

$$\Rightarrow a^3 \left[\frac{1}{2} \times 2 \right] = a^3$$

So ,

$$\Rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{a^3}{2^i} = a^3$$

Now we got a the left term can also be expressed in terms of the radius of sphere, i.e., the sum of the volumes of each sphere.

$$\Rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{4}{3}\pi r_i^3 \right) = a^3$$

$$\Rightarrow a = \left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{4}{3}\pi r_i^3 \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

The edge of the cube is expressed in the terms of the given expression, also this expression is just the summation of Volumes of the spheres.

Question 8 (Higher Degree polynomial)

Let $f(x) = ax^4 + bx^3 + cx^2 + dx + e$ be the quartic polynomial, where two of its roots are rational and two of the roots are irrational. The irrational roots of the polynomial are given by $\sqrt{p+q} = \sqrt{7}$, $\sqrt{pq} = \sqrt{10}$ where p and q are rational roots. Then find the quartic polynomial

Difficulty: MEDIUM

Prerequisites: Polynomials, Evaluation of roots of Quadratic polynomials, algebra.

Solution: Given that two of the roots of quartic polynomial are $\sqrt{7}$ and $\sqrt{10}$ which are irrational and are given by $\sqrt{p+q} = \sqrt{7}$, $\sqrt{pq} = 10$ in which p and q are rational roots.

$$\Rightarrow p + q = 7, pq = 10$$

if $q = 7 - p$ then,

$$\Rightarrow p(7 - p) = 10$$

$$\Rightarrow 7p - p^2 = 10$$

$$\Rightarrow p^2 - 7p + 10 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (p - 5)(p - 2) = 0$$

So $p = 2, p = 5$ are the rational roots of the quartic polynomial

Then the quartic polynomial is given by:

$$\Rightarrow (x - 2)(x - 5)(x - \sqrt{7})(x - \sqrt{10}) = 0$$

Expanding the expression we get,

$$\Rightarrow f(x) = x^4 - (\sqrt{7} + \sqrt{10} + 7)x^3 + (\sqrt{70} + 7\sqrt{7} + 7\sqrt{10} + 10)x^2 - (7\sqrt{70} + 10\sqrt{7} + 10\sqrt{10})x + 10\sqrt{70}$$

This question is based on understanding the Roots of a polynomial and evaluation of the polynomial using its roots (the points where the polynomial results in zero).

Question 9 (Double Progressions)

Let two arithmetic progressions be defined as:

$$A_1 = \alpha, \alpha + \delta, \alpha + 2\delta, \alpha + 3\delta, \dots$$

$$A_2 = \alpha, \alpha - \delta, \alpha - 2\delta, \alpha - 3\delta, \dots$$

If the $(2\beta - 1)^{th}$ term of A_1 , $(2\beta + 1)^{th}$ term of A_2 , $(2\beta)^{th}$ term of A_1 are in Geometric Progression respectively then find the value of δ in terms of α and β , $\delta \neq 0$.

Difficulty: MEDIUM

Prerequisites: Geometric Progression

Solution: Given that,

$(2\beta - 1)^{th}$ term of A_1 , $(2\beta + 1)^{th}$ term of A_2 , $(2\beta)^{th}$ term of A_1 are in Geometric Progression.

So, in Geometric Progression (middle term)²=(first term)×(last term)

$$\Rightarrow [(2\beta + 1)^{th} \text{ term of } A_2]^2 = [(2\beta - 1)^{th} \text{ term of } A_1][(2\beta)^{th} \text{ term of } A_1]$$

$$\Rightarrow [\alpha - [(2\beta + 1) - 1]\delta]^2 = [\alpha + [(2\beta - 1) - 1]\delta][\alpha + [(2\beta) - 1]\delta]$$

$$\Rightarrow [\alpha - 2\beta\delta]^2 = [\alpha + (2\beta - 2)\delta][\alpha + (2\beta - 1)\delta]$$

$$\Rightarrow \alpha^2 - 4\alpha\beta\delta + 4\beta^2\delta^2 = \alpha^2 + \alpha(4\beta - 3)\delta + (4\beta^2 - 6\beta + 2)\delta^2$$

$$\Rightarrow 4\beta^2\delta^2 - 4\alpha\beta\delta = (4\beta - 3)\alpha\delta + (4\beta^2 - 6\beta + 2)\delta^2$$

$$\Rightarrow 4\beta^2\delta^2 - (4\beta^2 - 6\beta + 2)\delta^2 = (4\beta - 3)\alpha\delta + 4\alpha\beta\delta$$

$$\Rightarrow (4\beta^2 - 4\beta^2 + 6\beta - 2)\delta^2 = (4\beta - 3 + 4\beta)\alpha\delta$$

$$\Rightarrow (6\beta - 2)\delta^2 = (8\beta - 3)\alpha\delta$$

$$\Rightarrow (6\beta - 2)\delta^2 - (8\beta - 3)\alpha\delta = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \delta[(6\beta - 2)\delta - (8\beta - 3)\alpha] = 0$$

So either $\delta = 0$ (Trivial case) or $[(6\beta - 2)\delta - (8\beta - 3)\alpha] = 0$

Since $d \neq 0$, we get

$$\Rightarrow [(6\beta - 2)\delta - (8\beta - 3)\alpha] = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (6\beta - 2)\delta = (8\beta - 3)\alpha$$

$$\Rightarrow \boxed{\delta = \frac{\alpha(8\beta-3)}{6\beta-3}}$$

So the common difference for the Arithmetic progression must be the condition mentioned above, and we also have another value $\delta = 0$, as it's mentioned in the question that consider $\delta \neq 0$.

If $\delta = 0$ all the terms of both the progression will be same so that's why we generally don't consider the common difference as zero in any question until and unless it's mentioned in the question.

Question 10 (Cylinder & Spheres)

If a cylindrical tank with radius R and height H is full of water up to the top level and some random metal spheres are dropped in the tank with radii r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4 and r_5 which displaces $\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{3}{7}$ and $\frac{5}{8}$ of the water present in the tank respectively one after one. What will be the ratio of the radii of the spheres and also find the rate of change of volume of the water displaced by the Spheres with respect to radius of the cylinder, while the height of the cylinder remains constant and curved surface area being $\frac{7}{3}$ sq. units

Difficulty: HARD

Prerequisites: Volumes , Rate measure

Solution: The volume of tank = $\pi R^2 H$, The spheres displaces the water in it. Let the initial volume of the tank be $V_0, V_0 = \pi R^2 H$

Each time a Sphere is dropped in the Cylindrical tank some of the water displaces out from the body, and when another Sphere is dropped in it, the fraction of the remaining water displaces. This continues till the last sphere is dropped.

The amount of water left in the cylindrical tank can be given by the table in which we have to find The volume displaced by the spheres each time

<u>Spheres</u>	<u>Volume of water displaced by it(given)</u>	<u>Actual volume of water with respect to the remaining water</u>	<u>Remaining volume of water</u>
Sphere-1	$\frac{1}{4}$	$V'_1 = V_0 \times \frac{1}{4} = \frac{V_0}{4}$	$V_1 = V_0 - V'_1$ $V_1 = \frac{3}{4}V_0$
Sphere-2	$\frac{1}{5}$	$V'_2 = V_1 \times \frac{1}{5} = \frac{3V_0}{20}$	$V_2 = V_1 - V'_2$ $V_2 = \frac{3}{5}V_0$
Sphere-3	$\frac{1}{3}$	$V'_3 = V_2 \times \frac{1}{3} = \frac{1}{5}V_0$	$V_3 = V_2 - V'_3$ $V_3 = \frac{2}{5}V_0$
Sphere-4	$\frac{3}{7}$	$V'_4 = V_3 \times \frac{3}{7} = \frac{6}{35}V_0$	$V_4 = V_3 - V'_4$ $V_4 = \frac{8}{35}V_0$
Sphere-5	$\frac{5}{8}$	$V'_5 = V_4 \times \frac{5}{8} = \frac{1}{7}V_0$	$V_5 = V_4 - V'_5$ $V_5 = \frac{3}{35}V_0$

Table(1.1)

As we know the volume of water displaced = volume of sphere.

- $(\frac{1}{4})^{\text{th}}$ of initial volume of cylinder = volume of sphere with radius r_1
 $\Rightarrow \frac{1}{4}\pi R^2 H = \frac{4}{3}\pi r_1^3$
 $\Rightarrow \frac{3}{16}R^2 H = r_1^3$
 $\Rightarrow r_1 = \left(\frac{3}{16}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} R^{\frac{2}{3}} H^{\frac{1}{3}} \dots(\text{i})$
- $(\frac{3}{20})^{\text{th}}$ of initial volume of cylinder = volume of sphere with radius r_2
 $\Rightarrow \frac{3}{20}\pi R^2 H = \frac{4}{3}\pi r_2^3$
 $\Rightarrow \frac{9}{80}R^2 H = r_2^3$
 $\Rightarrow r_2 = \left(\frac{9}{80}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} R^{\frac{2}{3}} H^{\frac{1}{3}} \dots(\text{ii})$

- $(1/5)^{\text{th}}$ of initial volume of cylinder = volume of sphere with radius r_3

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{5}\pi R^2 H = \frac{4}{3}\pi r_3^3$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{3}{20}R^2 H = r_3^3$$

$$\Rightarrow r_3 = \left(\frac{3}{20}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} R^{\frac{2}{3}} H^{\frac{1}{3}} \dots(\text{iii})$$
- $(3/7)^{\text{th}}$ of initial volume of cylinder = volume of sphere with radius r_4

$$\Rightarrow \frac{6}{35}\pi R^2 H = \frac{4}{3}\pi r_4^3$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{9}{70}R^2 H = r_4^3$$

$$\Rightarrow r_4 = \left(\frac{9}{70}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} R^{\frac{2}{3}} H^{\frac{1}{3}} \dots(\text{iv})$$
- $(1/7)^{\text{th}}$ of initial volume of cylinder = volume of sphere with radius r_5

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{7}\pi R^2 H = \frac{4}{3}\pi r_5^3$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{3}{28}R^2 H = r_5^3$$

$$\Rightarrow r_5 = \left(\frac{3}{28}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} R^{\frac{2}{3}} H^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

So the radii of the spheres are proportional to height and radius of the cylinder. Then the ratio of the spheres is given as

$$\Rightarrow r_1:r_2:r_3:r_4:r_5 = \left(\frac{3}{16}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} : \left(\frac{9}{80}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} : \left(\frac{3}{20}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} : \left(\frac{9}{70}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} : \left(\frac{3}{28}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

As we see the smallest term in this ratio is $\left(\frac{3}{28}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$ so dividing every term with it we get:

$$\Rightarrow r_1:r_2:r_3:r_4:r_5 = \left(\frac{7}{4}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} : \left(\frac{21}{20}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} : \left(\frac{7}{5}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} : \left(\frac{6}{5}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} : 1$$

Then taking the L.C.M of $20^{\frac{1}{3}}$ we get

$$\Rightarrow r_1:r_2:r_3:r_4:r_5 = (35)^{\frac{1}{3}} : (21)^{\frac{1}{3}} : (28)^{\frac{1}{3}} : (24)^{\frac{1}{3}} : (20)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

Now, we can see from the table(1.1) that the portion of $(1/7)^{\text{th}}$ of initial volume of water is still left in the tank. Then the volume of water that is displaced by the spheres is given by:

$$\Rightarrow V_L = V_0 - \frac{1}{7}V_0 = \frac{6}{7}V_0 \text{ where } V_L \text{ is the volume displaced by spheres}$$

So, the rate of change of the volume with respect to its radius, that is displaced by the spheres while height of the tank remains constant is,

$$\frac{d}{dr}V_L = \frac{d}{dr}\left(\frac{6}{7}\pi R^2H\right)$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{dV_L}{dr} = 2 \times \frac{6}{7}\pi RH \quad \left[\frac{d}{dx}x^n = nx^{n-1}\right]$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{dV_L}{dr} = \frac{6}{7}(2\pi RH)$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{dV_L}{dr} = \frac{6}{7} \times (\text{C.S.A}), \text{ C.S.A is termed as curved surface area.}$$

Given that the curved surface area of the cylinder is $\frac{7}{3} \text{ sq. units}$, Also the curved surface area of cylinder is $2\pi RH$.

$$\text{So, } 2\pi RH = \frac{7}{3} \text{ sq. units}$$

Then,

$$\Rightarrow \frac{dV_L}{dr} = \frac{6}{7} \times \frac{7}{3} = 2 \text{ cubic units/unit}$$

The rate of change of the volume with respect to its radius, that is displaced by the spheres of different radii Is 2 cu. units/unit or 2 sq. units .

Question 11 (Infinitely Composed Imaginary Function)

Let the function $f(x) = \text{Cot}\left(\text{Cot}\left(\text{Cot}(\dots(x))\right)\right)$ where the cotangent is infinitely composed and converges to a complex number.

Suppose the values $f'(x), [f'(x)]^2, [f'(x)]^3, \dots [f'(x)]^n$ form a geometric progression with alternate complex terms and first term as Complex number.

Then find the value of $\sum_{k=1}^n [f'(x)]^k$

Difficulty: HARD

Prerequisites: Differentiation of infinitely composed Functions, Complex numbers, Geometric Progression

Solution: Given that $f(x) = \text{Cot}\left(\text{Cot}\left(\text{Cot}(\dots(x))\right)\right)$ converges then,

$$\Rightarrow f(x) = \text{Cot}(f(x))$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{Cot}^{-1}[f(x)] = f(x)$$

Now differentiate both sides with respect to 'x'

$$\Rightarrow \frac{d}{dx} [\text{Cot}^{-1}(f(x))] = \frac{d}{dx} f(x)$$

$$\Rightarrow -\frac{f'(x)}{1+[f(x)]^2} = f'(x)$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{1+[f(x)]^2} = -1$$

$$\Rightarrow 1 + f(x)^2 = -1$$

$$\Rightarrow f(x)^2 = -2$$

$$\Rightarrow f(x) = \pm\sqrt{2}i$$

Then, $f(x)^2 = -2, f(x)^3 = \mp 2\sqrt{2}i, f(x)^4 = 4, \dots$

Case-I) If $f(x) = \sqrt{2}i$

Then, $f(x)^2 = 2i^2, f(x)^3 = 2\sqrt{2}i^3, f(x)^4 = 4i^4, \dots$

$\Rightarrow f(x) = \sqrt{2}i, f(x)^2 = -2, f(x)^3 = -2\sqrt{2}i, f(x)^4 = 4$

Here common ratio $r = \sqrt{2}i$

So, $\sum_{k=1}^n f(x)^k = \sqrt{2}i - 2 - 2\sqrt{2}i + 4, \dots$

Separating the real and complex terms we get:

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{k=1}^n f(x)^k = (-2 + 4 - 8 + \dots) + (1 - 2 + 4 - 8 + \dots)\sqrt{2}i$$

Then $r_R = -2, r_C = -2$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{k=1}^n f(x)^k = -2 \left(\frac{(-2)^n - 1}{2 - 1} \right) + \left(\frac{(-2)^n - 1}{2 - 1} \right) \sqrt{2}i$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{k=1}^n f(x)^k = \sqrt{2}((-2)^n - 1)(-\sqrt{2} + i)$$

Case-II) If $f(x) = -\sqrt{2}i$

$\Rightarrow f(x) = -\sqrt{2}i, f(x)^2 = -2, f(x)^3 = +2\sqrt{2}i, f(x)^4 = 4, \dots$

So, $\sum_{k=1}^n f(x)^k = -\sqrt{2}i - 2 + 2\sqrt{2}i + 4, \dots$

Separating the real and complex terms we get:

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{k=1}^n f(x)^k = (-2 + 4 - 8 + \dots) + (-1 + 2 - 4 + 8 + \dots)\sqrt{2}i$$

Then, $r_R = -2, r_C = -2$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{k=1}^n f(x)^k = -\sqrt{2}((-2)^n - 1)(\sqrt{2} + i)$$

Question 12 (Jacobian's Transformation)

Let,

$$u = \ln(\sec x + \tan x) + y \sin z, v = \ln(\tan x) + yz, w = \tan^{-1}(y) + \ln(\sin z)$$

Assume the transformation $(x, y, z) \leftrightarrow (u, v, w)$ is bijective and

differentiable at the neighborhood of $(x = \frac{\pi}{4}, y = 1, z = \frac{\pi}{2})$ Then

$$\text{let, } \left[\frac{\partial(x,y,z)}{\partial(u,v,w)} \right]_{(x=\frac{\pi}{4}, y=1, z=\frac{\pi}{2})} = \lambda$$

Then find the real roots of $\lambda^4 t^2 + \frac{16}{\lambda^2} t - \frac{21\lambda^6}{8} = 0$, where t is a

variable

Difficulty: HARD

Prerequisites: Partial derivatives, Jacobian Determinant, Determinants, quadratic equations.

Solution: Given that the transformation is from (x, y, z) to (u, v, w) taking the partial derivatives u, v, w with respect to x, y, z individually

Partial derivatives

$$u = \ln(\sec x + \tan x) + y \sin z$$

- $\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \sec x$
- $\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \sin z$
- $\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} = y \cos z$

$$v = \ln(\tan x) + yz$$

- $\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = \sec x \cdot \operatorname{cosec} x$

- $\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = z$
- $\frac{\partial v}{\partial z} = y$

$$w = \text{Tan}^{-1}(y) + \ln(\text{Sin } z)$$

- $\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} = 0$
- $\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{1+y^2}$
- $\frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = \text{Cot } z$

By forming jacobian determinant we get,

$$J = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \text{Sec } x & \text{Sin } z & y\text{Cos } z \\ \text{Sec } x \cdot \text{Cosec } x & z & y \\ 0 & \frac{1}{1+y^2} & \text{Cot } z \end{vmatrix}$$

At the points $(x = \frac{\pi}{4}, y = 1, z = \frac{\pi}{2})$

$$\Rightarrow J = \begin{vmatrix} \text{Sec } \frac{\pi}{4} & \text{Sin } \frac{\pi}{2} & \frac{(1)\text{Cos}\pi}{2} \\ \text{Sec } \frac{\pi}{4} \cdot \text{Cosec } \frac{\pi}{4} & \frac{\pi}{2} & 1 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{1+1^2} & \text{Cot } \frac{\pi}{2} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\Rightarrow J = \left[\frac{\partial(x,y,z)}{\partial(u,v,w)} \right]_{(x=\frac{\pi}{4}, y=1, z=\frac{\pi}{2})} = \begin{vmatrix} \sqrt{2} & 1 & 0 \\ 2 & \frac{\pi}{2} & 1 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\Rightarrow J = \sqrt{2} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cdot 0 - 1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \right) - 1(2 \cdot 0 - 1 \cdot 0) + 0 \left(2 \cdot \frac{1}{2} - 1 \cdot 0 \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow J = -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

As we have the value of J , then $\lambda = \frac{1}{J}$ because,

$$J = \left[\frac{\partial(u,v,w)}{\partial(x,y,z)} \right]_{(x=\frac{\pi}{4}, y=1, z=\frac{\pi}{2})}$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda = \left[\frac{\partial(x,y,z)}{\partial(u,v,w)} \right]_{(x=\frac{\pi}{4}, y=1, z=\frac{\pi}{2})} = \frac{1}{\left[\frac{\partial(u,v,w)}{\partial(x,y,z)} \right]_{(x=\frac{\pi}{4}, y=1, z=\frac{\pi}{2})}} = \frac{1}{J}$$

$$\Rightarrow \boxed{\lambda = -\sqrt{2}}$$

Then evaluating $\lambda^4 t^2 + \frac{16}{\lambda^2} t - \frac{21\lambda^6}{8} = 0$, we get

$$(\sqrt{2})^4 t^2 + \frac{16}{(\sqrt{2})^2} t - \frac{21(\sqrt{2})^6}{8} = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow 4t^2 + 8t - 21 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow 4t^2 + 14t - 6t - 21 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (2t - 3)(2t + 7) = 0$$

So roots of the equation are $t = \frac{3}{2}$ and $t = -\frac{7}{2}$

$$\Rightarrow \boxed{t = \left\{ \frac{3}{2}, -\frac{7}{2} \right\}}$$

This question deals with jacobian determinant of first order

Partial derivatives, I got to know about this concept when I was a bit bored while solving integration problems.

Question 13 (β & Γ Functions)

If I_1 and I_2 expressions are given as follow:

$$I_1 = \int_0^1 x^{8\sin(e^a)-1} (1-x)^{12\cos(e^b)-1} dx, I_2 = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^{11}\theta \cdot \cos^{13}\theta d\theta$$

Then find the value of $(I_1 + I_2)_{a=\ln(\frac{\pi}{6}), b=\ln(\frac{\pi}{3})}$

Difficulty: Hard

Prerequisites: Beta-Gamma functions, integration and permutations

Solution: As we know

$$\rightarrow \int_0^1 x^{m-1} (1-x)^{n-1} dx = B(m, n) \dots (i),$$

$$\rightarrow \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} (\sin \theta)^{2m-1} \cdot (\cos \theta)^{2n-1} \cdot d\theta = \frac{1}{2} B(m, n) \dots (ii)$$

Compare I_1 with equation (i) when $a = \ln\left(\frac{\pi}{6}\right)$, $b = \ln\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right)$

$$\Rightarrow I_1 = \int_0^1 x^{8\sin(e^{\ln(\frac{\pi}{6})})-1} (1-x)^{12\cos(e^{\ln(\frac{\pi}{3})})-1} dx$$

$$\Rightarrow I_1 = \int_0^1 x^{8\sin(\frac{\pi}{6})-1} (1-x)^{12\cos(\frac{\pi}{3})-1} dx$$

$$\Rightarrow I_1 = \int_0^1 x^{8 \cdot \frac{1}{2}-1} (1-x)^{12 \cdot \frac{1}{2}-1} dx$$

$$\Rightarrow I_1 = \int_0^1 x^{4-1} (1-x)^{6-1} dx$$

$$\Rightarrow I_1 = B(4, 6)$$

Comparing I_2 with equation (ii)

$$\Rightarrow I_2 = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^{11} \cdot \cos^{13} \theta d\theta = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} (\sin \theta)^{2 \cdot 6-1} \cdot (\cos \theta)^{2 \cdot 7-1} \cdot d\theta$$

$$\Rightarrow I_2 = B(6,7)$$

As we got the values of I_1 and I_2 at $a = \ln(\pi/6)$, $b = \ln(\pi/3)$

To evaluate beta function values we need to express it in terms of gamma function, i.e.,

$$B(m, n) = \frac{\Gamma(m) \cdot \Gamma(n)}{\Gamma(m+n)}$$

And the values of $\Gamma(n)$ are given by

- $\Gamma(n + 1) = n!$
- $\Gamma(1) = 1$
- $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\pi}$

$$\text{Then } (I_1 + I_2)_{a=\ln(\frac{\pi}{6}), b=\ln(\frac{\pi}{3})} = B(4,6) + B(6,7)$$

$$= \frac{\Gamma(4) \cdot \Gamma(6)}{\Gamma(4+6)} + \frac{\Gamma(6) \cdot \Gamma(7)}{\Gamma(6+7)}$$

$$= \frac{\Gamma(4) \cdot \Gamma(6)}{\Gamma(10)} + \frac{\Gamma(6) \cdot \Gamma(7)}{\Gamma(13)}$$

$$= \frac{3! \cdot 5!}{9!} + \frac{5! \cdot 6!}{12!}$$

$$= \frac{1}{504} + \frac{1}{5544}$$

$$= \frac{1}{462}$$

$$\Rightarrow \boxed{(I_1 + I_2)_{a=\ln(\frac{\pi}{6}), b=\ln(\frac{\pi}{3})} = \frac{1}{462}}$$

Question 14 (Sets: Unions & Intersections)

Let E_1, E_2 and E_3 be the 3 universal disjoint sets of A_i, B_j, C_k such that,

$$A_1 \subseteq A_2 \subseteq A_3, \dots \subseteq A_p, \quad B_1 \subseteq B_2 \subseteq B_3 \dots \subseteq B_q, \quad C_1 \subseteq C_2 \subseteq C_3 \dots \subseteq C_r$$

And the number of elements in each set is given by $|A_i| = 2^i$,

$|B_j| = 4j + 3$ and $|C_k| = 3k^2 - k + 2$ then find the value of,

$$\left(\sqrt{\left| \bigcup_{i=1}^{10} A_i \right|} + \left| \bigcap_{k=1}^{50} C_k \right|^2 + \left| \bigcup_{j=1}^{100} B_j \right| \right)_{min}$$

Difficulty: Easy

Prerequisites: Set theory, unions and intersections

Solution: As given above the universal sets are disjoint then it's clear that

$$A_i \cap B_j \cap C_k = \phi$$

It's also given that the preceding sets of each A_i, B_j and C_k are subsets to their succeeding sets so for the minimum value we have to assume that they are equal subsets, Then

$$\left| \bigcup_{i=1}^{10} A_i \right|_{min} = 2^{10} \Rightarrow \sqrt{\left| \bigcup_{i=1}^{10} A_i \right|_{min}} = \sqrt{2^{10}} = 2^5$$

$$\left| \bigcap_{k=1}^{50} C_k \right|_{min}^2 = 16, \quad \left| \bigcup_{j=1}^{100} B_j \right|_{min} = 403$$

$$\Rightarrow \left(\sqrt{\left| \bigcup_{i=1}^{10} A_i \right|} + \left| \bigcap_{k=1}^{50} C_k \right|^2 + \left| \bigcup_{j=1}^{100} B_j \right| \right)_{min} = 2^5 + 16 + 403 = 451$$

Question 15 (Probability & Trigonometry Trap)

A person is standing on a road facing a tower. He assumes the height of as x meters and the distance between him and the tower as y meters, if he wants to calculate the angle of inclination using the trigonometric functions, what is the probability that he chooses the Cosecant Function to find out angle of inclination? Why? And what will be the probability that he chooses Cotangent function?

Difficulty: Easy

Prerequisites: Probability, Logic

Solution: The person knows that the height of tower and distance between him and tower as x and y Respectively,

As the person only have the height of the tower and distance between him and the tower he either have to choose Tangent or Cotangent function in order to know the angle of inclination

So the probability of choosing the Cosecant Function is 0 and the probability of choosing Cotangent function is $1/2$.